

**PATHOGENETIC AND PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE
MARKERS OF IMMUNE INFLAMMATION IN
ASYMPTOMATIC ATHEROSCLEROSIS**

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Objectives: According to the available literature data, the SCORE scale for asymptomatic atherosclerosis (ALS) is not informative enough due to underestimation of the maximum values of risk indicators.

The aim of the study was to develop an algorithm for stratifying the 5-year risk of adverse cardiovascular events (ACS, fatal and non-fatal MI, cerebral stroke, development of atrial fibrillation) in individuals with confirmed instrumental methods of ALS, without concomitant cardiovascular diseases, not suffering from diabetes mellitus, based on the analysis of traditional risk factors and markers immune inflammation

Material and methods: 114 people suffering from asymptomatic atherosclerosis were monitored for 5 years. Traditional risk factors (gender, age, smoking index, total cholesterol level, SAD level, abdominal obesity (AO) and hf-CRP level) were initially assessed and circulating markers of immune inflammation (IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6, total antibodies to collagen I and Type III

(a-K), antibodies to sulfated glycosaminoglycans (sGAG) and to hyaluronic acid (HA)). Using cluster analysis, the contribution of traditional risk factors and markers of immune inflammation to the achievement of endpoints by patients (ACS, fatal and non-fatal MI, cerebral stroke, development of atrial fibrillation) was determined, followed by the determination of the most effective indicators using ROC analysis,

calculation of the discriminatory value and construction of a prognostic model based on the profile of traditional FR with the inclusion in this model of indicators of circulating markers of ED and immune inflammation as additional classifiers. Such indicators as RR, CI, HR and NNT were used for comparative evaluation of efficiency.

Results: According to the results of cluster analysis with ALS, the greatest classical risk factors such as age, smoking index (IC) and abdominal obesity contributed to the development of adverse cardiovascular events; among the circulating markers of ED and immune inflammation were levels of IL-1 β , a-K, antibodies to sGAG and to GC. According to the results of the ROC analysis, all classical risk factors have confirmed their effectiveness (age with a

discriminatory value of 57 years, smoking index with a discriminatory value of 15 years and the presence of abdominal obesity). Among the markers of ED and immune inflammation, the effectiveness was confirmed by the levels of autoantibodies to GC (discriminant 1.82 U), a-K (discriminant 0.23 mcg/ml), serum concentration of antibodies to sGAG (discriminant 1.7 U) and the level of IL-1 β (discriminant 66 pg/ml). We found that in ALS, age older than 57 years is associated with a 2.5-fold (RR 2.53) increase in the 5-year risk of adverse vascular events at NNT 7.9; IC over 15 years - with a 3.5-fold (RR 3.50) significant increase in risk at NNT 5.6, and the presence of AO - with more than A 6-fold (RR 6.92) increase in risk at NNT 6.1. The profile of traditional risk factors at the discriminative values determined by us reliably identified individuals with RR 4.82 (CI 2.00-11.61) at NNT 3.3. Serum concentrations of autoantibodies to HA exceeding 1.82 U were associated with a more than 7-fold (RR 7.51) significant increase in the risk of adverse cardiovascular events at NNT 4.5. Concentrations of a-K greater than 0.23 mcg/ml were associated with a more than 8-fold (RR 8.33) significant increase in the risk of adverse cardiovascular events at NNT 3.4. Concentrations of autoantibodies to sGAG greater than 1.7 U, was associated with more than 5-fold (RR 5,14) a significant increase in the 5-year risk of adverse cardiovascular events in NNT 4.3. The serum IL-1 β content exceeding 66 pg/ml was associated with a more than 2-fold (RR 2.82) significant increase in the risk of adverse cardiovascular events at NNT 7.0. When traditional risk factors are included in the profile of the indicator of antibodies to GC, individuals with RR 6.6 (CI 3.01-14.51), NNT 2.0 and HR 1.40 are identified. When turned on in the profile of traditional risk factors of the a-K index, individuals with RR 7.28, CI (3.38-15.69) are identified with a simultaneous decrease in the NNT index to 1.8 and HR 2.06. When included in the IL-1 β level, individuals with RR 8,50, CI (3.91-18.47) are detected? the indicator is NNT 1,7 and HR 2,00. When the level of autoantibodies to sGAG is included in the profile, individuals with RR 7.14, (CI3.19-15.97), NNT 2.0 and HR 0.95 are detected.

Conclusion: Thus, in order to identify patients at extreme risk for ALS to the profile of traditional risk factors, including age, IR with discriminatory indicators defined by us, and the presence of AO, from a practical point of view, it is most effective to use the IL-1 β level (discriminant 66 pg/ml; HR 2.0) and the a-level as classifiers.K (discriminant 0.23 mcg/ml; HR 2.1) as

indicators with the best analytical characteristics.